

SLM-Conditioned Hierarchical Relation Routing for Labeled Property Graph Learning

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Abstract. Labeled property graphs combine relational structure with heterogeneous textual and categorical properties attached to both nodes and relationships. Conventional graph neural networks typically represent these properties as static feature vectors, limiting their ability to determine which semantic evidence should influence message propagation for a particular prediction target. We propose SLM-Conditioned Hierarchical Relation Routing, an architecture that integrates a small language model directly into graph message selection. A topology GNN provides a stable structural representation and prediction anchor. For each target node, incident messages combine the neighbor’s structural state, node-property encoding, relationship-property encoding, and relationship type. A parameter-efficient SLM processes structured graph soft tokens and produces a target-conditioned routing query. This query first selects relevant messages within each relationship type and subsequently routes information across relation-level summaries. The resulting representation provides a bounded residual update to the topology anchor, preserving structural evidence while allowing contextual semantic information to modify the prediction. The architecture supports interpretable analysis at both the neighbor and relationship-type levels and provides a general mechanism for integrating language-derived semantics into property-rich graph learning.

Keywords: Labeled property graphs · Graph neural networks · Small language models · Hierarchical relation routing · Semantic message passing

1 Introduction

Labeled property graphs (LPGs) represent entities and relationships together with labels and heterogeneous properties. Unlike conventional attributed graphs, LPGs may associate rich semantic information with both nodes and relationships. A relationship can therefore communicate not only that two entities are connected, but also the context, category, time, amount, description, or other attributes of that connection. This representation is widely used in operational graph databases, including applications in healthcare, financial analysis, recommendation, cybersecurity, and network management.

Graph neural networks (GNNs) provide an effective mechanism for learning from relational structure. However, common GNN architectures either ignore textual properties or encode them once and treat the resulting vectors as static features. Such integration does not determine whether a particular property, neighboring entity, or relationship type is relevant to the current prediction target. This is especially limiting in heterogeneous LPGs, where a node may participate in many semantically different relationships.

Language models provide contextual representations of textual and structured properties, but using them only as feature encoders separates semantic interpretation from graph propagation. Conversely, converting complete neighborhoods into text may discard graph structure and quickly exceed the language model context window. A useful integration should preserve explicit graph topology while allowing language-derived context to control the flow of relational evidence.

We introduce *SLM-Conditioned Hierarchical Relation Routing*, an architecture in which a small language model (SLM) directly conditions GNN message selection. A topology GNN first produces a stable structural representation and prediction anchor. Incident messages contain structural neighbor states, semantic node and relationship encodings, and relationship-type information. A parameter-efficient SLM derives a target-conditioned query that routes these messages in two stages: first within individual relationship types and then across relation-level summaries. The routed evidence produces a bounded residual update to the structural prediction.

The proposed formulation has three principal characteristics. First, it maintains a clear structural path through the topology GNN. Second, it introduces semantic conditioning inside message propagation rather than only at the input or output layer. Third, its hierarchical organization exposes neighbor-level and relation-level routing weights, enabling analysis of the evidence used for individual predictions.

2 Related Work

Classical message-passing GNNs aggregate information from local graph neighborhoods. GCN uses normalized neighborhood convolution [1], GraphSAGE introduces inductive neighborhood aggregation [2], and GAT learns attention weights between connected nodes [3]. These methods primarily assume node-attributed graphs and do not explicitly address target-conditioned interpretation of rich node and relationship properties.

Graph Transformers extend attention to broader structural contexts. Graphormer incorporates structural encodings into Transformer attention [4], while GraphGPS combines local message passing with global attention [5]. Their attention mechanisms are, however, learned from graph representations rather than conditioned by an adapted language model interpreting property-level evidence.

Recent studies combine graphs with language models. GraphGPT applies graph instruction tuning to language models [6], whereas GraphLLM augments

language-model reasoning with graph representations [7]. Existing work largely focuses on expressing graphs for language models or using language models for graph reasoning. Our method instead retains explicit GNN propagation and uses an SLM-generated query to route incident messages hierarchically within and across LPG relationship types.

3 Method

Let an LPG be defined as

$$\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \tau_V, \tau_E, \mathbf{P}_V, \mathbf{P}_E),$$

where \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{E} denote nodes and relationships, τ_V and τ_E are their labels or types, and \mathbf{P}_V and \mathbf{P}_E contain their property maps. For a target node v , the objective is to predict an output y_v using its structural neighborhood and property-derived semantic evidence.

3.1 Structural Anchor

A topology GNN operates on graph connectivity and type information to produce structural node states:

$$\mathbf{h}_v^{(l+1)} = \text{GNN}^{(l)} \left(\mathbf{h}_v^{(l)}, \left\{ \mathbf{h}_u^{(l)} : (u, v) \in \mathcal{E} \right\} \right).$$

The final structural representation $\mathbf{h}_v^{\text{top}}$ is mapped to anchor logits

$$\mathbf{z}_v^{\text{top}} = f_{\text{anchor}}(\mathbf{h}_v^{\text{top}}).$$

This prediction path provides a stable reference that does not depend on the SLM successfully interpreting every property.

3.2 Semantic LPG Encoding

Node and relationship property maps are serialized into semantic atoms containing labels, property names, and property values. An SLM encoder maps them to fixed-dimensional representations:

$$\mathbf{s}_v = \text{Enc}(\mathbf{P}_V(v), \tau_V(v)), \quad \mathbf{s}_{uv} = \text{Enc}(\mathbf{P}_E(u, v), \tau_E(u, v)).$$

For every relationship (u, v) incident to target v , we construct a message candidate

$$\mathbf{x}_{uv} = [\mathbf{h}_u^{\text{top}} \parallel \mathbf{s}_u \parallel \mathbf{s}_{uv} \parallel \mathbf{e}_{\tau_E(u, v)}],$$

where $\mathbf{e}_{\tau_E(u, v)}$ represents the relationship type and \parallel denotes concatenation. Thus, each candidate contains structural, node-semantic, relationship-semantic, and schema-level evidence.

3.3 SLM-Conditioned Query

Structured graph views, target semantics, and anchor decision features are projected into the embedding space of a small language model and prepended to a short textual prompt as soft tokens. The SLM is adapted using low-rank adaptation while its base parameters remain quantized. Its final hidden state produces the routing query

$$\mathbf{q}_v = \text{norm}(f_q(\text{SLM}(\mathbf{T}_v))),$$

where \mathbf{T}_v denotes the target-specific soft-token sequence.

The query also modulates message values using feature-wise affine transformations:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_{uv} = \mathbf{v}_{uv} \odot (1 + \gamma(\mathbf{q}_v)) + \beta(\mathbf{q}_v).$$

This allows the SLM to influence both message importance and message content.

3.4 Hierarchical Relation Routing

Routing is performed in two stages. First, candidate messages are grouped according to their relationship type r . Within each group, attention weights are calculated as

$$\alpha_{uv}^{(r)} = \frac{\exp(\mathbf{q}_v^\top \mathbf{k}_{uv})}{\sum_{(j,v):\tau_E(j,v)=r} \exp(\mathbf{q}_v^\top \mathbf{k}_{jv})}.$$

A relation-specific summary is then obtained:

$$\mathbf{c}_{v,r} = \sum_{(u,v):\tau_E(u,v)=r} \alpha_{uv}^{(r)} \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_{uv} + \mathbf{e}_r.$$

The second stage routes information across the available relation summaries:

$$\beta_{v,r} = \frac{\exp(\mathbf{q}_v^\top \mathbf{k}_{v,r})}{\sum_{r' \in \mathcal{R}_v} \exp(\mathbf{q}_v^\top \mathbf{k}_{v,r'})},$$

where \mathcal{R}_v is the set of relationship types incident to v . The final routed message is

$$\mathbf{m}_v = \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}_v} \beta_{v,r} \mathbf{v}_{v,r}.$$

This decomposition prevents numerous relationships of one type from directly competing with isolated relationships of another type. It also provides two complementary explanations: $\alpha_{uv}^{(r)}$ identifies relevant neighbors within a relation, while $\beta_{v,r}$ identifies relevant relation types.

3.5 Bounded Residual Prediction

The routed message updates the structural target state:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_v = \text{LayerNorm}(\mathbf{h}_v^{\text{top}} + \mathbf{m}_v).$$

A residual head predicts a bounded correction:

$$\Delta \mathbf{z}_v = \tanh\left(f_{\Delta}\left([\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_v \parallel \mathbf{m}_v]\right)\right),$$

and the final prediction is

$$\mathbf{z}_v = \mathbf{z}_v^{\text{top}} + \delta_{\max} \Delta \mathbf{z}_v.$$

The bound δ_{\max} prevents semantic routing from arbitrarily replacing the structural prediction. For regression, the same formulation can be used with scalar anchor and residual outputs.

The model is optimized using the supervised prediction loss together with an auxiliary SLM verbalizer loss. Only the LoRA parameters, soft-token projections, routing modules, and residual head require adaptation. Cached semantic encodings and low-bit SLM quantization make training feasible on a single consumer GPU.

3.6 Implementation Details

We use Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct [10] as the small language model. Node and relationship property atoms are encoded with the same model using a maximum sequence length of 128 tokens. During hierarchical routing, the SLM is loaded using four-bit NF4 quantization and adapted with LoRA [8, 9]. LoRA is applied to the query, key, value, and output projections with rank 8 and scaling parameter 16. The base SLM parameters remain frozen.

The routing model uses up to 32 incident relationships per target. Training uses five-fold stratified cross-validation and five random seeds. Semantic property encodings are cached before training. Quantized SLM computation uses bfloat16 precision, gradient clipping, and a short LoRA-only warm-up period. These settings allow the complete model to be trained using a single NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU.

4 Experimental Results

The healthcare dataset was obtained from the publicly available Neo4j Healthcare Analytics graph example.¹ The repository contains data from the FDA Adverse Event Reporting System (FAERS), represented using cases, drugs, substances, indications, reactions, manufacturers, therapies, report sources, and demographic attributes.

¹ <https://github.com/neo4j-graph-examples/healthcare-analytics>

Table 1. Healthcare adverse-event death-outcome prediction. Results are mean \pm standard deviation over five seeds, with five folds per seed. The best result in each column is shown in bold.

Model	Accuracy	Balanced Acc.	Macro-F1	AUROC	AUPRC
Topology GNN	0.844 \pm 0.007	0.561 \pm 0.008	0.546 \pm 0.006	0.634 \pm 0.005	0.133 \pm 0.006
Node-semantic static GNN	0.890 \pm 0.008	0.621 \pm 0.027	0.619 \pm 0.024	0.742 \pm 0.051	0.300 \pm 0.050
Edge-semantic static GNN	0.882 \pm 0.013	0.642 \pm 0.022	0.629 \pm 0.027	0.751 \pm 0.037	0.304 \pm 0.054
Hierarchical relation router	0.907 \pm 0.010	0.692 \pm 0.023	0.687 \pm 0.023	0.799 \pm 0.022	0.363 \pm 0.038

We reconstructed the graph directly from the CSV files distributed with the repository. The resulting LPG contains 11,948 nodes and 91,090 relationships. The prediction targets are 4,307 **Case** nodes, of which 329 are associated with a death outcome. Outcome records were used exclusively to construct labels and were not included in the input graph. Report identifiers and other collection-related identifiers were also excluded from semantic features to reduce the possibility of target leakage.

The task was evaluated using five random seeds, with five stratified folds per seed. We report the mean and standard deviation across the five seed-level means. Because the positive class constitutes only approximately 7.6% of the target nodes, macro-F1, balanced accuracy, AUROC, and AUPRC are more informative than accuracy alone.

The proposed model was compared with three architectural baselines: a topology-only GNN, a node-semantic static GNN, and an edge-semantic static GNN. The node-semantic model initializes nodes using SLM-derived property encodings, whereas the edge-semantic model additionally incorporates encoded relationship properties into message propagation. In both semantic baselines, the encodings remain static and do not perform target-conditioned routing.

The hierarchical relation router obtains the best mean result for every reported metric. Relative to the strongest static baseline for the respective metric, it improves accuracy by 1.6 percentage points, balanced accuracy by 5.0 points, macro-F1 by 5.8 points, AUROC by 4.8 points, and AUPRC by 5.9 points. The improvements in macro-F1 and AUPRC are particularly relevant for this imbalanced task. Moreover, the relatively small variation across seeds indicates that the improvement is not attributable to a single favorable data split.

The difference between the topology-only and static semantic baselines confirms that node and relationship properties carry useful predictive evidence. However, the further improvement obtained by the proposed model suggests that encoding this evidence is not sufficient by itself. Target-conditioned selection within relationship types and across relation-level summaries provides additional value beyond static semantic message passing.

5 Conclusion

We presented SLM-Conditioned Hierarchical Relation Routing, a method for integrating language-derived semantics directly into message propagation over

labeled property graphs. The architecture retains a topology-GNN anchor while using a parameter-efficient SLM to determine which neighboring messages and relationship types are relevant to each target. Its two-stage routing mechanism separates evidence selection within relationship types from selection across relationship types, while a bounded residual update protects the structural prediction from unstable semantic corrections.

The method addresses a central difficulty of property-rich graph learning: node and relationship properties should not merely be encoded, but should influence propagation according to the target and its relational context. Future work will investigate regression, link-level prediction, larger LPG schemas, alternative semantic encoders, and the use of routing distributions for explanation and model auditing.

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